

Understanding Employer Branding: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

Organizations working in the high-tech sector are particularly benefitting from Employer Branding as a growing field of practise. As a result of its multiple advantages, it has attracted the curiosity of academics in numerous domains and opened countless new study pathways. Employer branding articles have exploded in popularity in recent years, prompting academics to do studies on the topic. As a result, the purpose of this paper was to examine the body of work that has been indexed in Web of Science on Employer Branding from 1999 to 2021. Biblioshiny, an R-package for bibliometric analysis, was used to examine the most prestigious journals and publications using bibliometrix R-package. The researchers culled through 158 pieces of literature for this one. Results showed that there is considerable interest in the topic and that literature on this subject is still in its infancy. Global Business Review, International Journal of Organizational Analysis, Journal of Brand Management and Journal of Product and Brand Management were the most popular journals in terms of number of articles published each year. Employer branding articles from the United States and Europe had the most citations, with a combined total of 151, according to Edward MR, 2010, Personnel Review. This list includes the most prolific authors in the field of scientific study during a period of time: Dabirian A; Prasad A; Lieven F; Wawer M; Kietzmann J; and Bendarviciene R; Attractiveness was mentioned 31 times in the publications, image was mentioned 23 times, and recruitment was mentioned 18 times, according to keyword analysis. Research in this field reveals the social and intellectual structure, which teaches future researchers about developing subjects, situations, and partnership possibilities. Employer branding and attractiveness are linked in this study by bringing together disparate literature, identifying relevant sources, authors, and documents, and by examining the relationship between the two.

Keywords:Employer Brand, Employer Branding, Talent Management, Employer Attractiveness, Bibliometric

Introductions:

One of the biggest challenges organizations have been facing in recent years has been attracting and retaining talent. As we move away from a production-based economy to a knowledge-based economy, skilled people are increasingly becoming the source of

sustainable competitive advantage (Moroko & Uncles, 2008). Petkovic (2008) posits that the labour market is changing from a sellers' market to a buyers' market. In this context, employer branding is becoming increasingly important in firms as a means of attracting and retaining talent. The research (K. B. Backhaus, 2004) looked into the constituents of corporate image that are given in the descriptions, as well as how companies promote their employer branding. Employer branding refers to a company's effort to convey, both internally and externally, a clear picture of what makes it unique and desirable as an employer (K. Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004). The findings (Raml & Kenning, 2014) showed that the brand personality trait 'sincerity' influences both employer brand trust and affect.

Further research revealed that the appeal of an employer's brand might be significantly boosted by employer branding activities. (Wilden et al., 2010) investigated the nature and consequences of employer branding. According to a study, potential employees usually assess the attractiveness of employers based on any prior direct job experience with the company or in the sector. (Lievens et al., 2007) worked on studies of organizational identity and employer branding (employer image) and found outsiders' assessments of the firm are equally important to employees.

Employer branding study focuses on how attractive an organisation is to potential fresh recruits, as well as study and writing related to the psychological contract literature and work on corporate image, identification, and personal traits (Edwards, 2009). From the standpoint of potential employees, (Berthon et al., 2005) defined and operationalized the elements of employer attractiveness. In addition, (K. Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004) argued the connection among employer branding and organizational career management. Recent research has highlighted the importance of employer branding in maintaining, inspiring, and engaging employees in order to achieve higher productivity. As a result, employer branding not just aids in the recruitment of the best possible people, but it also aids in the efficiency and productivity of a business.

Employer branding is a strategy for attracting and retaining talented employees by establishing the company as an industry's 'employer of choice'. By combining the principles of HRM and Brand Marketing, (Ambler & Barrow, 1996) were the first to create the phrase employer branding. The employer brand's external marketing is generally intended to attract the target audience, but it can also be used to promote and enhance the product or company brands. Employer branding demands that the employer brand be aligned with the firm's other branding activities (Ambler & Barrow, 1996). It is also the aggregate of a company's efforts to communicate to current and potential employees that it is an attractive place to work (Lloyd, 2002). As per There are two components to an employer's brand. Employee value proposition (EVP) describes what employees receive as 'value' while working for the company, and 'employee experience' describes how that value is delivered (Rosethorn, 2020).

Methods:

Employer Branding/Employer Brands were retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection between 1999 and 2021. (WoS). Many academics and researchers have access to databases like Scopus, EBSCO, Science Direct, ProQuest, or PubMed. Web of Science is a Clarivate Analytics (Formerly Thomson Reuters) service, however it's often considered the

most precise and complete source for scientific discovery and evaluation, with the best quality indexing. Researchers also consider that comparisons between various authors, organisations or fields of study are more useful (Aldieri et al., 2019; Ronda-Pupo et al., 2015).

The bibliometrix R-package in R-studio was used to process and analyse the WoS database for bibliometric variables. When conducting the research, it was decided to use the title (tt) field instead of the topic (tp). The tt field includes titles, abstracts, and keywords (from authors and keywords plus). "Employer Brand" OR "Employer Branding*" were the key search phrases. Document Types: Articles or Proceedings Papers or Early Access, and Languages: English. After entering this string, the system displayed 158 documents pertaining to Employer Branding/Employer Brands.

Results and Quantitative Analysis:

Between 1999 and 2021, the Web of Science database yielded 158 papers, with an average citation count of 11.63 and an average citation rate of 1.781 per year. Articles (99) and proceedings papers (100) are the most often published document types (43).

There were 322 authors and 368 author appearances in the extracted publications, which had a collaboration index of 2.53. A total of 32 articles are written by a single person. Table 1 provides a summary of the gathered research publications.

Table 1: Description about data collected from Web of Science databases

Description	Results
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2007:2021
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	122
Documents	158
Average years from publication	3.89
Average citations per documents	11.63
Average citations per year per doc	1.781
References	5079
DOCUMENT TYPES	
article	99
article; early access	6
article; proceedings paper	2
correction; early access	1
proceedings paper	43
review	6
review; book chapter	1
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	242
Author's Keywords (DE)	426
AUTHORS	
Authors	322

Author Appearances	368
Authors of single-authored documents	29
Authors of multi-authored documents	293
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored documents	32
Documents per Author	0.491
Authors per Document	2.04
Co-Authors per Documents	2.33
Collaboration Index	2.33

Fig. 1 Number of papers published by year during the 1999-2021 period.

Fig. 2 Three Field Plots.

Sankey Plots can be used to show the relationship between three fields, with the size of each component according to the datatype value. Plots like this one can be used to show how many sources and authors were studied, as well as how many keywords were used. Things like Employer Branding and their sources and significant authors were displayed on each of the items. Major media referred to "Employer Branding," suggesting that it has a significant impact on the quality of services.

Prominent Journals:

Employer Branding-related publications have been published in a number of high-volume journals, which are shown in Table 2. In terms of number of publications, these are the top four most prominent journals. Three times a year in the International Journal of Organizational Analysis and three times a year in Global Business Review (3).

Table 2: Top 20 prominent journals

Sources	Articles
Education Excellence and Innovation Management: A 2025 Vision to Sustain Economic Development During Global Challenges	4
Industrial and Commercial Training	4
International Journal of Organizational Analysis	4
Global Business Review	3
International Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals	3
Journal of Brand Management	3
Journal of Product and Brand Management	3
Management Review	3
Pacific Business Review International	3
Administrative Sciences	2
Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration	2
Business Horizons	2
Career Development International	2
Human Resource Development International	2
Human Resource Management	2
Innovation Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Value Chain In A Dynamic Environment	2
Jims8m-The Journal of Indian Management \& Strategy	2
Journal of Tourism and Services	2
Management \& Marketing-Challenges For The Knowledge Society	2
Management Research-The Journal of The Iberoamerican Academy of Management	2

Fig. 3 Most relevant affiliations

Top Relevant Authors and Authors Impacts

With four articles in the field, Dabirian A, was the most prolific author (Fig. 5). There are three articles on this subject by Prasad A. Lieven F. Wawer M. Kietzmann J. and Bendarvicene R. Based on their h-indexes, Lieven F had the greatest h-index among the authors, according to a study (Figure 4). They make a big difference. These papers are significant in terms of future research in this field. Among the most prolific researchers in the field are Dabirian A, Kietzmann J, and Wawer M.

Fig. 4 Social impact by H index

Fig. 5 Most Relevant Authors

Fig. 6 Source local impact by H-index

Most Global Cited Documents

From 1999 to 2021, the WoS database yielded the top 20 most widely referenced publications on Employer Branding. Each of these articles contains over 30 citations. Data shows that the most often cited papers are Edwards MR, 2010, (151), Lievens F, 2007 (131), Foster C, 2010 (120), Wilden R, 2010 (119), and Silvertzen AM, 2013 (119). (106). Major reference articles in the field are those that have received the most citations from other journals.

Table 3: Most global cited documents

Paper	DOI	Total Citations	TC per Year
EDWARDS MR, 2010, PERS REV	10.1108/00483481011012809	151	12.6
LIEVENS F, 2007, HUM RESOUR MANAG	10.1002/hrm.20145	131	8.7
FOSTER C, 2010, J PROD BRAND MANAG	10.1108/10610421011085712	120	10.0
WILDEN R, 2010, J MARKET MANAG	10.1080/02672570903577091	119	9.9
SIVERTZEN AM, 2013, J PROD BRAND MANAG	10.1108/JPBM-09-2013-0393	106	11.8
LIEVENS F, 2016, ANNUAL REVIEW OF ORGANIZATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY AND ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR, VOL 3	10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-041015-062501	95	15.8
DAVIES G, 2008, EUR J MARKET	10.1108/03090560810862570	92	6.6
MARTIN G, 2011, INT J HUM RESOUR MANAG	10.1080/09585192.2011.560880	70	6.4
AGGERHOLM H, 2011, CORP COMMUN	10.1108/135632811111141642	60	5.5
APP S, 2012, MANAG REV	10.5771/0935-9915-2012-3-262	54	5.4
THEURER CP, 2018, INT J MANAG REV	10.1111/ijmr.12121	52	13.0
BISWAS MK, 2016, J BUS ETHICS	10.1007/s10551-014-2502-3	46	7.7
DABIRIAN A, 2017, BUS HORIZ	10.1016/j.bushor.2016.11.005	45	9.0
ELVING WJL, 2013, J BRAND MANAG	10.1057/bm.2012.21	44	4.9
MOROKO L, 2009, J BRAND MANAG	10.1057/bm.2009.10	41	3.2
CHHABRA NL, 2014, INT J ORGAN ANAL	10.1108/IJOA-09-2011-0513	39	4.9
VAN HOYE G, 2013, APPL PSYCHOL -INT REV -PSYCHOL APPL -REV INT	10.1111/j.1464-0597.2012.00495.x	39	4.3
TANWAR K, 2016, GLOB BUS REV	10.1177/09721509166	33	5.5

	31214		
ALNIACIK E, 2012, 8TH INTERNATIONAL STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT CONFERENCE	10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.1117	33	3.3
CASCIO WF, 2014, HUM RESOUR DEV INT	10.1080/13678868.2014.886443	30	3.8

Fig. 7 Most global cited documents

Most Cited Countries and Author’s Country Production

It is clear from Table 4 that industrialised countries have contributed more to the literature than developing countries. Using data from 1999 to 2021, we found the top 20 most productive author countries on Employer Branding. Following Poland (36), Portugal (29) and Germany (29), India has the highest number of published documents, according to the data (28).

Research in this field is concentrated in the United Kingdom, which has received 456 mentions. India and Poland rise in the rankings due to their strong performance in related production. These findings could indicate that underdeveloped countries are making continuous progress toward high-quality research in the field.

Table 4: Most cited countries and author’s country production

Most cited countries		Country’s scientific production	
Country	Total Citations	Country	Frequency
United Kingdom	456	India	91
Belgium	270	Poland	36
India	244	Portugal	29
Australia	162	Germany	28
Germany	137	Czech Republic	23
Norway	106	USA	22
Denmark	60	UK	20
Sweden	57	Sweden	13

Turkey	55	China	12
Netherlands	54	Canada	11
USA	39	Australia	10
Croatia	29	Belgium	10
Canada	25	Slovakia	10
Czech Republic	24	Austria	8
Finland	16	Croatia	8
Malaysia	13	Lithuania	8
France	12	Netherlands	8
New Zealand	11	Turkey	8
Russia	11	Indonesia	7
Portugal	9	Pakistan	7

Keyword Analysis:

According to an analysis of the frequency of keywords used in the articles, "attractiveness" occurred 31 times, followed by "image" 23 times, "recruitment" 18 times, "performance" 14 times, "identity" 14 times, "reputation" 12 times, "commitment" 12 times, "model" times 12, and "impact" 12 times. The magnitude of the words in Fig. 8's word cloud illustrates how frequently they appear in the article. The literary importance of the word can be omitted.

Fig. 8 Word cloud - visualization of the words that appeared most frequently in the papers

Trend Topics:

Logarithmic frequency values on the vertical axis and publication years on the horizontal axis are shown in Figure 9 to show the progression of top trending themes. There was a clear trend throughout the past five years' worth of topics. 2016 and 2017 saw a lot of attention paid to models, organisational attractiveness, and employee-organization fit. As of 2018 to 2020, the

focus has been on image, job satisfaction and attractiveness as well as recruitment. From 2010 to 2020, the topic of employer brand equity has been extensively studied.

Fig. 9 Trend Topics

Thematic Map:

Maps of typological themes can be plotted on a two-dimensional design. Through the use of co-word analysis, the research topic's themes can be discovered. On a two-dimensional graph, these themes can be divided into four groups based on their density and centrality, which are the two variables. As depicted in Fig. 10, the concept "attractiveness" is a core theme, indicating an important yet underdeveloped sector. Talent, business orientation, recruiting, image, job choice, perceptions, behaviours, and mediation roles are all examples of niche themes in the top left quadrant that are well-developed with inbound links but have poor external ties and are only marginally significant.

Fig. 10 Thematic map based on density and centrality

Conceptual Structural Map:

Employee Branding publications from 1999 to 2021 were divided into two clusters of 8 and 56 items in each with elements focusing on organisation attributes (employer brand equity), image, and identity in the red cluster. Job happiness and work engagement are among the characteristics of the blue cluster. Figure 11 illustrates this point.

Fig. 11 Share Conceptual Structural Map in Published Documents

Social Network Analysis

The links within the research issue were discovered through the application of social network analysis (Zupic & Čater, 2015) Associating nodes reflect the social network's relationships with participants such as authors, organisations, or publication platforms (Fig. 12). The system that connects various domains depicts the movement of the network. Using cooperation networks based on significant countries, geographic dispersion and collaboration were examined. A global perspective shows that most European countries, Australia, and emerging economies rely on US-led scholarly research.

Fig. 12Country Collaboration Map

Limitations and Future Directions:

A comprehensive list of the most-cited journals, nations, articles, and countries was compiled using corresponding sources by the author. There are also other flaws in the research. For example, the bibliometric examination of recently released excellent articles has been neglected or omitted. This is a drawback associated with the weight that citation volume has on an article's impact. It's impossible to gauge an article's influence and advancement in an area or industry just on the basis of how many citations it has. Preference for articles published in English-speaking journals is strongly influenced by the language of publication. The fact that a country's scientists publish and collaborate at a lower rate should in no way be construed as an indication of the quality of that country's research.

This bibliometric investigation makes use of the WoS database. Data from other databases could be used in future investigations. It is possible that more keywords might be incorporated into the keyword search to allow for the inclusion of other relevant publications. Theoretical and conceptual details can be gleaned from meta-analytic reviews and in-depth content analyses of works related to this subject. Researchers will benefit from studying the elements that affect all of Employer Branding and these areas of decision-making.

Conclusion:

Using data from 1999 through 2021, this study compares the world's best journals, the most frequently cited articles, and the most influential writers in the field of employer branding. Recruiting, job satisfaction, and organisational dimensions were among the top trending topics from 2018 to 2020. Information on research findings from related authors, country collaborations, and relevant countries are all included in this bibliometric analysis as well. Scientific reports, evaluations, and visualisations based on Employer Brand/Employer Branding research will all be made easier as a result of this. Employer Branding, in particular, has the potential for continued growth in this sector with the use of certain topics and phrases.

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